

Evaluation of The World Factbook

BIBLIOGRAPHIC INFORMATION

Title	The World Factbook
<u>Authority</u>	
Author	Directorate of Intelligence, US CIA
Publisher	Central Intelligence Agency, US
<u>Imprint Information</u>	
Place of Publication	Washington, D.C (United States)

Year of Publication	First Edition : August 1962 Latest Edition : Online (last updated on 17th October, 2019)
<u>Other Information</u>	
Language	American English
Periodicity	Weekly

INTRODUCTION

The World Factbook is also known as the CIA World Factbook, is a reference source produced by the Central Intelligence Agency (CIA) with almanac-style information about the countries of the world.

It provides information on the history, people and society, government, economy, energy, geography, communications, transportation, military, and transnational issues for 267 world entities.

The World Factbook gives brief and factual updated information on world nations. Collection of basic intelligence information on the countries of the world.

History

The first, classified, edition of Factbook was published in August 1962, and the first unclassified version in June 1971. The World Factbook was first available to the public in print in 1975. In 2008 the CIA discontinued printing the Factbook themselves, instead turning printing responsibilities over to the Government Printing Office. This happened due to a CIA decision to "focus Factbook resources" on the online edition. The Factbook has been on the World Wide Web since October 1994.

SCOPE

The World Factbook is prepared by the CIA for the use of U.S. government officials, and its style, format, coverage, and content are primarily designed to meet their requirements. However, it is frequently used as a resource for academic research papers and news articles.

- **Coverage** - Internationally available and usage. Countries included from Afghanistan to Zimbabwe + European Union

TREATMENT

- On the top Factbook webpage contains a dropdown list for selecting the country which will provide you the country wise updated facts. (*Default it is set to the World*)
- Web page has very simple Graphical User Interface with few tabs. The Three major Divisions of tabs are - ABOUT, REFERENCES, APPENDICES.
- In **About** tab further expansion of list contains-
 - History
 - Copyright and Contributors
 - Did you know? (Facts on World Factbook)
 - Customer Comments
- It has important **References** tab which contains sublist of -
 - Regional and World Maps
 - Flags of the World
 - Gallery of Covers (contains the cover of Factbook prepared by graphic designers)
 - Definition and Notes (contains the terms and criteria used to represent some specific info like acronyms used)
 - Guide to Country Profile (simple guide to Categories, field and subfield)
 - Guide to Country Comparison (Countries comparison pages are generally given in descending order - highest to lowest - such as Population and Area)
- Another tab is of **Appendices** has sublist of -
 - Abbreviations
 - International Organizations and Group
 - Selected International Environmental Agreements
 - Cross-Reference list of Country Data Codes (Geopolitical Entities and Codes:GCE, ISO etc)
 - Cross-Reference list of Geographic names (with Long, Lat)
 - Weights and Measures
 - Strategic Material
- The content for the country contains –
Expandable list view include brief of :
 - Introduction
 - Geography

- People and Society
- Government
- Economy
- Energy
- Communication
- Transportation
- Military and Security
- Terrorism
- Transnational issues

- The World Factbook is more **biased** toward US.

ARRANGEMENT

- On World Factbook's home page the information is arranged chronologically in descending order of dates.
- As per user will scroll down it will provide the earlier factual events of a particular country.
- Also alphabetical arrangement of Countries In flag of the world tab which directly redirect to countries information or profile.
- Cross-Reference lists are also arranged alphabetical Country wise.
- Use of American English in every aspect.

FORMAT

World Factbook is available in following different formats-

- **Web Version**

- Freely accessible, easy to use and navigate to particular info.
- Weekly updates on home page under *What's New* section

- **Archive of World Factbook**

- Replica of web version available free to download which provide World Factbook information offline accessible through computer
- Annual updates

- **Print Format**

- As hardcopies are no longer produced after 2016-17 but can purchase printed copies from US Government Printing Office

- Some unofficial printed version still available by several publishers like Seahorse Publishing. (As CIA declared it as public domain so it can be copied without permission, but CIA's seal shouldn't be used in it).

- **Other**

- In past years, the Factbook was available in CD-ROM, Microfiche, magnetic tapes and floppy disk.

SPECIAL FEATURES

- ▶ Some features in Countries Profile are -
 - **One page Summary** on Countries information which is being further categorized under tabs.(pdf)
 - **Travel Facts** of a Country.(pdf)
 - **Images**
- ▶ Drop Down list for direct selection of country is a feature added for fast navigation to desired country's information.
- ▶ Maps are available to download (pdf and img format), three types of maps available -
 - Administrative
 - Physiography
 - Transportation
- ▶ Expansion of Country's information under profile is easy by just one click of *Open all*
- ▶ *Field listing* button is available in country's information to compare the same kind of information with other countries.
- ▶ Archive is available to download and use offline with maximum similar functionality to web version.
- ▶ The appendices tab add some features of abbreviations, international orgs. etc

LIMITATIONS

- Website is not mobile friendly, as per no mobile app is being developed.

- Information is much biased to US.
- The archive demands at least 4gigs of storage and 2 gigs of download. Also requires installation of some softwares.
- Some regions or areas of disputes aren't covered by World Factbook such as Kashmir.
- It's no longer available for hardcopy readers.

CONCLUSION

The CIA's World Factbook is one of most accessed publications of US Government produce information for US policymakers and coordinated throughout the US Intelligence Community, presents the basic realities about the world, shares facts with the people of all nations, the information includes data like political, geographical, economical, military etc.

The information collected from a wide variety of US Government agencies as well from hundreds of published source after evaluations so it's a reliable reference source of facts, statistics and information about the countries of the world.

Reviews by Government Officials-

1. Your website is excellent. It provides an indispensable reference for those involved in global political, military, diplomatic, or economic affairs. *[US Navy officer]*
2. I was looking at *The World Factbook* online. The site looks great! It is pleasant on the eyes, and of course, the content is a treasure trove. *[Executive Secretary for Foreign Names, US Board on Geographic Names]*

REFERENCES

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